
The Role of Skills in Sustainable Employment- A Review

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Abstract:

This research explores the existing literature regarding role of skills in sustainable employment. Sustainable employment relies on the ongoing growth and use of important skills. In the current fast-changing job market, employers look for candidates who have basic knowledge and can also adapt, innovate, and succeed in various settings. The purpose of the literature review is to assess the various skills for sustainable employment. Skill development is vital for creating jobs and improving livelihoods. In our rapidly changing world, the need for a skilled workforce is more important than ever. As industries change and new technologies arise, up skilling is necessary for both workers and companies. Developing skills is key to increasing job opportunities by closing the gap between employer needs and workforce capabilities.

Keywords: Skill Development, Employability, Training, Sustainability, Entrepreneurship, Technical and Vocational Education.

Introduction:

Skills are essential for making the best use of human resources. A skilled workforce is not only valuable but also necessary for long-term economic growth. The World Youth Skills Day 2022 emphasized "learning and skills for life, work, and sustainable development," especially during the current recovery phase. The rising youth population presents both challenges and opportunities for policymakers everywhere. The growing reliance on technology and the evolving job market highlight the need to equip young people with skills for employment and entrepreneurship. This will help them adapt to changes and become positive change-makers. Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) institutions play a crucial role in fostering entrepreneurial values that benefit young individuals, economic progress, and a sustainable society. A comprehensive approach is needed to integrate entrepreneurial learning and employable skills into vocational

training, preparing youth for jobs, decent work, and entrepreneurship. Collaboration among TVET institutions, businesses, labour unions, policymakers, think tanks, public policy experts, and development partners is essential to effectively implement skill development programs.

The National Education Policy-2020 is designed to meet future demands and challenges effectively. It aims to address skill shortages by promoting vocational education in schools. At least half of all students in both school and higher education will have access to vocational training. Offering one vocational course to each student before they finish 10+2 can make a significant impact.

Review of Literature:

Harishchandra J Sharma (2016), study titled "Employability Skill Literature Review in India", has examined the previous studies underlining the impact of skill in developing employability in India. The analytical skills, the skill of developing self-

understanding, the efficiency to improve general management and work culture, developing leadership quality, problem solving ability and communication skills are all responsible to increase the level of employability among the human resource in India. The employability level will help in bridging the skill gap and that could only be done when the higher education incorporates the skill as an essential part in their curriculum. The article focuses on the point that all those workers who have the multi-tasking ability can sustain in gainful employment for a longer duration.

Karanveer and Amandeep (2015) study titled “Skill Development in Higher Education: Trends and Issue”. This work has thrown light on the current scenario of higher education in our country. The demand for skill education is clearly felt throughout the educational system, particularly at the higher levels. The study focuses on the options available to students at higher levels and proposes several strategies to improve the learning pattern and incorporate skill development as an integral part of their syllabus. The study also states that India ranks seventh in the world in terms of filling job vacancies, indicating that the country is having significant difficulty in the fields of IT personnel, accounting and finance staff, receptionists, secretaries, office support staffs, legal staff, researchers, teachers, executive managers, nursing staffs, and others. Even though many universities have been established in the past decade, there has been little improvement in job market absorption. This is mainly due to the absence of effective skill and training programs in their syllabi and curricula. These universities tend to focus on traditional education methods instead of preparing students to meet the needs of the job market.

Meenal Sharma and Abhishek (2018) discuss the topic "Shifting Dynamics of Skills in India," focusing on the urgent need

to skill the youth for improved economic growth. With 62% of its population aged between 15 and 59, India, as the youngest nation, must quickly respond to harness its demographic advantage. Addressing this challenge now is crucial for India to develop a skilled workforce of 700 million by 2022. Additionally, the rise of technology and artificial intelligence presents a significant threat, as labour-intensive jobs are increasingly replaced by capital-intensive and automated methods. Therefore, it is essential to equip the population with modern skills to help them compete effectively and secure their futures.

Vandanasaini (2015) in her study titled “Skill Development in India : Need , Challenges and Ways Forward “ has given a detailed view on the current scenario of job market of our country and the need of skill development programme to be undertaken as the major initiative to deal with the problem of massive unemployment. The study discusses the demand and supply mismatch in the job market, the geographical difficulties faced by the youths, the low literacy rate with poor quality of learners, poor infrastructure, poor public private partnership, and informal- formal skill gaps etc. as the main reasons to hinder the economic growth of the nation.

Sanjeeb Hazarika (2016) in this study titled “Skill Development for Rural Entrepreneurship: A Study of State Institute of Rural Development (SIRD), Assam” that SIRD played an important role in Assam to provide various skill development training facilities specially focusing on rural development. Various programmes like building of Resource centre, Development and management of growth centre, common facility centre and resource centre in Information Technology division, SATCOM training programmes were also undertaken and conducted on a regular basis by SIRD. The research report also highlighted the fact

that lack of awareness is the main reason of low outcomes.

Conclusion:

From the above reviews it has found that, Employability is a multifaceted concept that requires attention from various stakeholders. By addressing the challenges and implementing strategic measures, India can empower its workforce to successfully navigate the dynamic job market. Improving employability is critical not only for individuals' professional growth, but also for the overall economic development of the country. Employers and hiring managers agree that having employability skills is essential for getting a job in the corporate world. Communication, attitude, leadership, decision-making, and teamwork are among the talents required. The empirical model tested the hypothesis that there is a substantial relationship between students' employability abilities and business and human resource strategies, particularly in terms of recruitment and training processes.

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